

AGREEMENT ON THE JOINT USE OF TRADEMARKS UNDER THE LEGISLATION OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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According to the legislation of Uzbekistan on trademarks, registration of a mark similar in terms of confusion with a trademark may be allowed with the consent of the right holder to register this mark (part four of article 10 of the Trademark Law). This raises a relevant question: in cases where consumers are confused when choosing goods, can the parties use the same trademark registration?

Before answering this question, it is necessary to determine the legal status of relations of this nature. That is, a trademark sharing agreement is governed by the terms of the agreement or by the law governing the terms of the agreement. The short answer to this question is that under a trademark sharing agreement, one party grants the other party the opportunity to register the same or a similar trademark with its own trademark. Therefore, this agreement cannot be equated to the status of a contractual relationship. The reason here is that the owner of the preferred trademark allows another person to register a trademark similar to their own trademark. In this case, the obligation arises only in relation to one party.

When it comes to the circulation of the same or similar trademarks, most lawyers, based on the definition given by the International Trademark Association, argue that the circulation of similar trademarks should not ultimately lead to their "mixing". The parties must take appropriate measures to prevent such a situation [1].

In general, the contents of a trademark sharing agreement may include: protection of a person using the same or misleadingly similar trademark with a priority trademark, exclusion of limiting the right of the owner of the priority trademark to bring a claim for infringement in the future to the next trademark owner;

the contract was concluded in order to prevent a decision on filing a trademark for registration with the patent office for registration, including refusal to register a trademark, appealing such a decision to higher authorities [2];

an agreement is concluded with the relevant companies in order to preliminary determine the areas of interest, the volume and territory of use of product markets and trademarks, as well as the registration of new trademarks; such agreements may also be concluded in the event of the alienation of the exclusive

right to a part of the goods as part of the merger and accession of a legal entity and to determine the limits of the coexistence of a legal entity in the commodity market in the future. A joint use agreement may also be concluded in the event of separation and separation of a legal entity in order to preserve the possibility of producing goods under the same or similar trademarks.

Compared to other countries, the United States has a relatively widespread practice of mutually agreeing trademark trade [3]. In addition, there is case law in the United States related to these relationships [4]. In the opinion of the US courts, the parties clearly understand the degree of confusion about these trademarks in connection with their joint use under the contract [5]. Based on this, the courts make their decisions. Also, the courts and the US Patent Office agree that a trademark sharing agreement can mislead consumers, and if the use of such a mark is contrary to the public interest, registration of this transaction is not allowed [6].

Attorney Spencer Willems argues [7] that the US courts are in favor of recognizing the coexistence of trademarks as legal and real under the law of obligations. Even a partial refusal to complete a transaction or a restriction of its exclusive right to a trademark may be recognized as a counter-norm to this Agreement.

Spencer Willems also agrees with Mariana Moss that the courts and patent offices should be allowed to intervene in the agreement with the consumer's interests in the community in mind when assessing the legality of the sharing agreement, and most importantly, consider the possibility of consumer error when using a trademark in this form. and possible negative consequences for it [8].

The Agreement on the joint use of trademarks in the European Union (hereinafter referred to as the EU) is not regulated by legislation at the Union level. The EU Directives do not regulate trademark sharing agreements, however, according to the fifth paragraph of article four of the EU Trademark Directive No. 2015/2436, if the owner of the preferred trademark has agreed to register the next trademark, the EU states should not refuse to register a trademark or impose an obligation to annulment of his legal protection [9].

It is emphasized that, in addition to the regulation of the EU Directive, agreements on the joint use of trademarks should be considered and evaluated in accordance with the provisions of a separate obligation of the EU countries [10]. The issue of compliance of the joint use agreement with the requirements of the antimonopoly legislation is also considered in the assessment from the

point of view of diverting the attention of consumers, as well as protecting their social interests [11].

German trademark law sets out the rules for sharing a trademark, and in some cases this relationship is also recognized as a "limitation agreement". While the treaty operates under the law of obligation, it does not extend the term of the obligation applicable to trademark owners. However, in practice, the agreement contains provisions to increase the restrictions on the right to the right holder [12].

In the United Kingdom, the use of trademarks is governed by the Trade Marks Act 1994. According to this law, if a trademark is granted to two or more persons, each of them has the right to receive a separate share of the trademark registered under the agreement. Any right holder can use a registered trademark on his own or through his representative to perform any actions that do not contradict the law, for the purpose of making a profit without the consent of other persons or without liability. However, the owner of the same trademark registered in his name may not present a license agreement, assign rights or transfer his interest in respect of this trademark to another person without the permission of other persons. Any other partner may sue the copyright holder for failing to comply with this requirement. If one or all of the parties do not enter the case as a plaintiff or defendant, the court has the right to reject the claim. The court does not take any financial action in relation to the person participating in the case as an additional defendant, this person only participates in the dispute as a participant [13].

China also has no legislation governing the trademark sharing agreement [14]. However, Chinese law does not deny the existence of this type of contract. In particular, according to article four of the State Law on Trademarks, the right to use trademarks in goods of the same type is registered only in relation to one person. Registration of similar marks at the same or misleading level is not allowed. At the same time, Chinese law also does not prohibit the sharing of trademarks by two or more persons [15].

Under Russian trademark law, care should be taken not to mislead consumers, especially when registering a trademark sharing agreement [16]. However, the courts do not take into account the fact that when considering disputes related to a contract of this nature, consumers may be mistaken. Courts pay attention only to the fact that the contract was concluded with the permission of the right holder and registered accordingly [17].

Conclusion.

In accordance with paragraphs two and three of Article 10, part one, paragraph 13 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin”, registration of identical marks can only be permitted with the consent of the trademark owner. In particular, the category of signs for which such consent is required includes signs that are identical or confusingly identical with well-known trademarks. Despite the presence of a rule on the joint use of a trademark, in paragraph 13, part one, Article 10 of this Law, such content is not directly defined.

At the same time, the current legislation provides for the rights and obligations of the parties under an agreement on the joint use of trademarks, the rights of a person using a trademark similar to a trademark (in particular, licensing, disposal of the right, leaving the right to his heirs, use as a pledge, disclaimer), as well as rules regarding the liability of trademark owners as a result of inadequate quality of products under similar trademarks.

However, it should be noted that an agreement on the use of a trademark cannot be attributed to the type of such agreements as an agreement on an exclusive right, on a license or on a refusal agreement. This Agreement does not grant exclusive rights to any trademark with an earlier priority date. However, according to part two, Article 3 of the Law “On Trademarks, Service Marks and Appellations of Origin”, an agreement of this nature does not correspond to the content of a collective trademark. In this type of civil law relations, the priority party is the owner of the trademark. Another person may, with the consent of the owner of the exclusive right, register a similar or preferably the same trademark.

An agreement on the joint use of a trademark does not have the property of a contract. The provisions of Articles 103 and 110 of the Civil Code apply to these relations. Such an agreement must be notarized.

A trademark sharing agreement may be recognized as an exclusive right, subject to the rules set out above. It follows that the absolute right to a mark is originally a fundamental right. This is due to the fact that a derivative right is independent of the original right that arose in the name of another person after a certain period of time. Such a right is in some respects a dependent right. The term "restricted right" as used in relation to this Agreement means that the secondary right is in the possession of the original right. For example, if the latter arises, although it can be used by the owner independently and receive income, cannot transfer the rights to the trademark to others, dispose of the right, use it as a

pledge, leave a will, or otherwise waive the right without the consent of the original copyright owner.

Based on this, the agreement on the joint use of a trademark can be described as follows: "The agreement on the joint use of a trademark is a civil law relationship associated with the registration and use of the same or similar trademarks by two or more persons with the consent of the trademark owner."

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